

Psychological Technique to Reduce the Psychological Illness of Athletes

Ravindra M. Ghoti ^{1*}, Aprana Astputre ²,

¹Shivaji Art's, comm. & Science college Kannad

²Babasaheb Marathwada University

Corresponding Author: Ravindra M. Ghoti ghoti.rm@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The present study has been conducted to investigate the Psychological Techniques to reduce the psychological illness of athletes. Study includes the athletes (Distract level players) in Aurangabad respectively who were between the age of 20 and 30. To assess the Anxiety and Frustration and factors of the subject the Shina's Anxiety inventory and Nayrashmapa Frustration test and Psychological Techniques is counseling and Guidance, Meditation, and Relaxations techniques. Research design is Pre-Post test. Proposed Statistical Procedure is Descriptive statistics i.e. Mean, S.D, will be computed and 't' test. Conclusion in this study On the basis of data and discussion of results, the hypotheses were tested and verified. Psychological illness of athletes tends to show reduced by Psychological techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Being an athlete requires a lot more than simply natural talent. All players in all sports must learn to handle the strain of competition, whether they are just getting started or planning to play professionally. But more often than not, the competition's result—whether you win or lose—is emphasised rather than the mental focus required to give your best performance.

Athletes have high expectations for themselves and frequently feel more pressure to perform well in order to avoid disappointing others. For athletes, the contrast between the thrill and satisfaction of victory and the heartache and sadness of defeat seems greater than in other situations. As a result, particularly at higher levels of competitiveness, mental weariness and other mental health problems may become more common..

A split-second choice can make or break your performance in practically every sport. You must maintain your composure, remain sharp, and be able to concentrate. However, if you have mental health issues or lack the mental clarity to make these choices, you run the risk of not just performing poorly but, more crucially, of gravely hurting yourself.

Your body's natural reaction to stress is anxiety. It is a sensation of dread and trepidation over what lies ahead. The majority of people might experience anxiety and panic on their first day of school, during a job interview, or when giving a speech. However, if your anxiety symptoms are severe, last for more than six months, and interfere with your life, you may be suffering from an anxiety disorder.

Frustration is a frequent emotional reaction to opposition that is related to anger, aggravation, and disappointment. It results from the perception of resistance to a person's will or purpose being fulfilled, and it is likely to get worse when a will or objective is denied or prevented. Internal and external frustration come in two flavors. Internal irritation can be brought on by difficulties achieving personal objectives, desires, innate urges, and requirements, as well as by coping with perceived flaws like low self-esteem or social anxiety.

The act of focusing your concentration on one thing at a time is known as meditation. It can entail concentrating on the breath, physical sensations, or a mantra, which is a word or phrase. In other words, meditation entails directing your attention away from nagging ideas and toward the here and now. Meditating is surprisingly easy.

In psychology, relaxation is the low-tension emotional state of a living being in which there is no arousal from emotions like anger, anxiety, or terror. the Oxford dictionary claims. When the body and mind are free of stress and tension, we say we are relaxed. A slight sedative is used by the backward cortex to transmit signals to the frontal cortex during relaxation, which is a sort of mild ecstasy emanating from the frontal lobe of the brain. Meditation, autogenic relaxation, and progressive muscle relaxation are all effective methods of relaxing.. Relaxation improves stress management. The main factor causing both physical and mental disorders is stress. So, having a good sense of relaxation is good for one's health. Because we are in a fight-or-flight response

mode when we are stressed, the sympathetic nervous system is activated; over time, this could have detrimental impacts on a human body.

In this study of the Aurangabad District, psychological techniques to lessen the psychological disease of athletes were investigated.

METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative research using a research design. The purpose of this study is to determine whether Using Psychological techniques to reduce psychological illness for athletes Players. Locus of the present investigation will be confined to the athletes (Distract level players) 100 subject will be taken from the population finally 20 athletes will select for this study from Aurangabad district . The stratified randomize sample taken into consideration for the study consisted of 20 athletes. The efforts will be made to have the sample as representative as possible in terms of area of living.

RESEARCH RESULT

Locus of the present investigation will be confined to the athletes (Distract level players) 100 subject will be taken from the population finally 20 athletes will select for this study from Aurangabad district . The stratified randomize sample taken into consideration for the study consisted of 20 athletes. The efforts will be made to have the sample as representative as possible in terms of area of living. The population was limited areas restricted Aurangabad District only. It can be spread into other areas also. The sample of the study was small. The study can also be done by taking large sample size. The tools used in this investigation were self - reporting instrument, it is therefore noted that the accuracy of data reported is limited to the abilities and willingness of the respondents to give truthful responses.

Hypotheses:

1. Anxiety of athletes can be reduced by Psychological techniques.
2. Frustration of athletes can be reduced by Psychological techniques.

Table 1. Design:- Quasi-experimental design (Time Series Design)

O₁ X O₂

O ₁	X	O ₂
Pre-test	After (ten day) Treatment	Post-test
1. Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety test (SCAT) 2. Nairashya Maapa (Frustration Test)	1. Meditation Relaxation Techniques	1. Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety test (SCAT) 2. Nairashya Maapa (Frustration Test)

Variables under Study:

Independent variable

1. Athletes (Distract level players)

Dependent variable

1. Frustration
2. Anxiety

Proposed Statistical Procedure:

1. Descriptive statistics i.e. Mean, S.D, will be computed.
2. 't' test

Description of the Self- Information

This schedule was saturated by to collect the following facts about the student.

Personal Information: Name, Sex, Age, Caste, occupation and yearly income
Types of players

Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety test (SCAT)

Constructed by A.K.P. Sinha and L.N.K Sinha in this test good validity and reliability.

DISCUSSION

Hypothesis No.1 *Anxiety of athletes can be reduced by Psychological techniques.*

Show the graph there are significant a difference between mean score of athletes Pre-test on Anxiety (50.5) is comparatively larger than the mean score of athletes Post-test on Anxiety (30.5). 't' value significant ($t=4.18$, $P < 0.001$ & 0.005 Level) difference between athletes Pre-test and Post-test on Anxiety.

Figure 2. Anxiety and Frustration

Hypothesis No.2. Frustration of athletes can be reduced by Psychological techniques.

Show the graph there are significant a difference between mean score of athletes Pre-test on Frustration (40.5) is comparatively larger than the mean score of athletes Post-test on Frustration 15.5). 't' value significant ($t=5.7$, $P < 0.001$ & 0.005 Level) difference between athletes Pre-test and Post-test on Frustration

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of data and discussion of results, the hypotheses were tested and verified. Some hypotheses were partially retained and some were rejected and following conclusions were drawn.

1. Anxiety of athletes tends to show reduced by Psychological techniques.
2. Frustration of athletes tends to show reduced by Psychological techniques

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